

RESEARCH ARTICLE

DIRECTION FOR REVITALIZING TUMENGGUNGAN MARKET IN KEBUMEN THROUGH THE STRENGTHENING OF URBAN HERITAGE IDENTITY

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Received: Mar 1 2026</p> <p>Accepted: Mar 12, 2026</p> <p>Keyword: Heritage Identity, Revitalization, Traditional Market</p> <p>*Corresponding Author: 1442200116@surel.untag-sby.ac.id</p>	<p><i>Tumenggungan Market is the largest traditional market in Kebumen Regency and plays a strategic role in sustaining the local economy, supporting social interaction, and forming part of the city's cultural heritage area. However, its current condition reveals several architectural issues, including irregular spatial zoning, narrow circulation paths, inadequate sanitation facilities, and the weak representation of local identity within the market's built form. This study aims to formulate the direction for the revitalization of Tumenggungan Market by integrating cultural, historical, and site-specific contextual factors. The research employs field observations, site analysis, and a literature review related to culturally grounded architectural approaches. The findings indicate that the revitalization of Tumenggungan Market should prioritize the preservation of Kebumen's heritage identity through the reinterpretation of local architectural elements and the strengthening of traditional market social-spatial characteristics. In addition, this study proposes architectural strategies to reinforce the cultural expression of the market's physical form, reorganize spatial zoning, and improve circulation quality as well as supporting facilities within the revitalization framework of Tumenggungan Market</i></p>

INTRODUCTION

Traditional markets constitute an important component of the economic structure and social life of communities. In addition to functioning as the primary distribution channel for local commodities, traditional markets also play a significant role in fulfilling the need for spaces of social interaction and cultural exchange, while simultaneously serving as a representation of the local identity of a particular region (Suryana, 2020). Within the context of urban areas, the presence of traditional markets is capable of representing the community's economic system while also reflecting local cultural values that have developed and been preserved across generations.

Tumenggungan Market, as the main market in Kebumen Regency, is located in a strategic position within the city's trade network. In addition to functioning as a center of commerce, the market is also situated near several heritage elements of the area, such as Alun-Alun Kebumen and Tugu Lawet. The presence of the market therefore represents not only the economic center of the region but also forms part of the historical urban structure through the visual and social identity of Kebumen.

However, the current condition of Tumenggungan Market reveals several issues that indicate a decline in spatial quality and a weakening of the local character traditionally associated with the market. Furthermore, the architectural form of the market building, which is the result of a previous revitalization effort, has not been able to express the local identity of Kebumen, resulting in a loss of connection with the historical and cultural context of the surrounding area.

On the other hand, regional policy directions such as the Regional Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMD) 2025-2029 and the Regional Spatial Plan (RTRW) of Kebumen Regency emphasize that the revitalization of traditional markets should be based on strengthening micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), preserving regional local identity, and improving adequate supporting facilities. Therefore, the revitalization of Tumenggungan Market needs to be formulated through an architectural approach capable of integrating local cultural values with the functional requirements of the market space.

Within this context, the direction of the revitalization of Tumenggungan Market needs to be oriented toward strengthening the city's heritage identity through an approach that integrates local cultural values with the characteristics of traditional spatial patterns. This includes principles rooted in local culture, distinctive patterns of social interaction, and visual elements that represent the identity of Kebumen. Such an approach aligns with the concept of Neo-Vernacular Architecture, which emphasizes the reinterpretation of local values through symbolic expressions within cultural contexts while accommodating contemporary technology and functional needs (Oliver, 2006; Sutanto, 2019).

Therefore, based on these issues, this research seeks to formulate the direction of the revitalization of Tumenggungan Market with an emphasis on strengthening local heritage identity while improving the functional quality of the market space.

Literature Review

Traditional Markets as Economic, Social, and Cultural Spaces

Traditional markets function as important economic and social nodes that facilitate social interaction and reflect the cultural life of surrounding communities. These markets typically develop organically over time and gradually become an integral component of the visual identity of the urban area (Suryana, 2020).

Heritage in the Urban Context

Heritage refers to a concept associated with the historical, cultural, architectural, and social values of a place. According to Jokilehto (1999), heritage is not limited to physical elements but also encompasses intangible values such as traditions, social

activities, and the relationship between people and space. In the urban context, the concept of heritage is intended to preserve local identity through the reinterpretation of characteristics that hold significant value for the community.

Traditional Market Revitalization Policies

The Ministry of Trade, through the Indonesian National Standard (SNI) for People's Markets, establishes market feasibility standards that include the physical condition of buildings, circulation systems, sanitation areas, and the spatial organization of market spaces. At the regional level, the Regional Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMD) of Kebumen Regency emphasizes that market revitalization should prioritize strengthening the local economy while preserving regional cultural identity.

Neo-Vernacular Architecture, Concepts, and Principles

Neo-vernacular architecture emerged as a response to the criticism of modernization that often neglects the importance of local context, including culture, climate, materials, and social heritage. The neo-vernacular approach seeks to integrate traditional vernacular values with contemporary functional requirements and technological developments in order to produce buildings that are more adaptive and rooted in local identity (Pratama et al., 2025).

Rather than merely imitating traditional forms, this approach reinterprets traditional principles such as climatic adaptation, the use of local materials, and culturally influenced spatial patterns into architectural expressions that meet contemporary standards of comfort, safety, and functionality.

According to Paul Oliver (2006), in his book *Built to Meet Needs: Cultural Issues in Vernacular Architecture*, neo-vernacular architecture in a contemporary context is grounded in several key principles :

1. The application of traditional elements, emphasizing a balance between tradition and modern innovation.
2. Responsiveness to tropical climate conditions in order to achieve passive environmental comfort.
3. The integration of cultural aesthetics and local identity as architectural markers that reinforce a building's connection to its cultural context.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a descriptive qualitative approach to understand the architectural, cultural, and environmental context of Tumenggungan Market as the basis for formulating the direction for market revitalization. This method is intended to systematically and factually describe the existing conditions in the field (Sugiyono, 2019).

Primary data were obtained through field observations focusing on community activity patterns as well as the spatial zoning and circulation conditions within the market area. These observations were used to identify several key issues, including irregular spatial zoning, narrow circulation paths, inadequate sanitation facilities, and the weak expression of local identity in the architectural form of the market building.

Secondary data were collected through literature review, including regional planning documents such as the Regional Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMD) and the Regional Spatial Plan (RTRW), the Indonesian National Standard (SNI) for People's Markets, as well as scholarly studies related to Neo-Vernacular Architectur. Through the analysis of the collected data, this study aims to formulate the direction of revitalization in order to preserve local heritage identity within the context of the revitalization of Tumenggungan Market in Kebumen Regency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Site Analysis

Tumenggungan Market is located in the center of Kebumen and functions as one of the city’s primary activity centers. The market is situated within a heritage area due to its proximity to prominent local landmarks such as Alun-Alun Kebumen and Tugu Lawet, as well as its position along the city’s main urban corridor. Beyond its strategic role as a commercial hub, Tumenggungan Market is also spatially integrated with the surrounding heritage district.

Figure 1. Location of Tumenggungan Market

Site Boundaries

Figure 2. Site Boundaries of Tumenggungan Market

Tumenggungan Market is located at Jl. Pahlawan No. 147, Keposan, Kebumen District, Kebumen Regency. The site boundaries of the market area are as follows :

- Northern boundary, Adjacent to Jl. Kolopaking, characterized by small to medium scale commercial activities.
- Eastern boundary, Adjacent to Jl. Kusuma, which functions as a retail corridor.
- Southern boundary, Adjacent to Jl. Soekarno-Hatta, one of the city’s primary urban corridors.
- Western boundary, Adjacent to Jl. Letnan Jenderal Suprpto, which is predominantly characterized by a dense residential area.

External Site Analysis

Site Climate Analysis

Figure 3. Dry Bulb x Relative Humidity

Figure 4. Temperatur Range

Air temperature and humidity characteristics ;

- During the dry season (June-September), temperatures generally range between 33°C and 34°C, with relative humidity around 50-55%.
- During the rainy season (December-March), temperatures range between 29°C and 31°C, while humidity levels increase significantly to approximately 90-100%.

Average monthly temperature conditions :

- The average high temperature ranges between 29°C and 32°C.
- The average low temperature ranges between 22°C and 24°C.
- The recorded highest temperature reaches approximately 33-35°C, typically occurring during the peak of the dry season (September-November).

- The recorded lowest temperature is approximately 20-21°C, generally occurring during the rainy season (January-March).

Sun Path Analysis

Figure 5. 07:30 9 (morning sun) (afternoon sun)

Figure 6. 12.30 (midday sun)

Figure 7. 16.30

Based on the sun path diagram presented above, the pattern of solar exposure across the site can be identified according to the orientation of each building façade:

Eastern Side

- Receives relatively intense solar exposure starting around 07:00 in the morning.
- This condition has the potential to increase the temperature of trading spaces during the early hours of market activity.

Southern Side

- At midday, the sun is positioned almost directly above the site, producing relatively strong solar radiation.
- Open areas such as the forecourt and pedestrian zones require adequate shading or protective elements to reduce heat exposure.

Western Side

- Receives the most intense solar radiation during the late afternoon.
- The accumulated heat from afternoon radiation tends to be retained until the evening, potentially increasing indoor temperatures within the market building.

Northern Side

- Receives minimal direct solar radiation.
- This orientation therefore has potential for functions that require higher levels of thermal comfort.

Wind and Noise Analysis of the Site

Figure 8. Wind Direction on the Site

Figure 9. Noise Levels on the Site

The prevailing wind at Tumenggungan Market blows from the southeast to the northwest at a speed of 1.5-2 m/s, which is above the typical standard of 0.4-0.8 m/s (SNI 03-6572-2001). This condition may affect natural ventilation and thermal comfort within the market.

Regarding noise levels, the market comfort standard (SNI 03-6386-2000) ranges from 60-70 dBA. To maintain comfort, noise mitigation measures—such as barriers or vegetation buffers—are recommended for the surrounding areas.

Analysis of Existing Views and Site Circulation

Existing Site Views

Figure 10. Existing Views

Figure 11. Existing Circulation

Based on the existing site views, the following observations can be made :

Eastern View

- The main façade of the market features a large gable roof with potential traditional value.
- The overall form appears rigid and leans toward a modern style.
- No architectural elements clearly express the local identity.

Southern View

- The culinary area covers the main market façade.
- The visual corridor of Jl. Pahlawan, the city’s main street, is obstructed and poorly organized.

Western View

- The building has a canopy; however, its design is overly simple (rectangular modules).
- Small openings and minimal ventilation reduce spatial comfort.

Northern View

- Visual quality is inadequate in terms of color and building module composition.
- No discernible local visual elements are present.

Based on the circulation map, the movement patterns at Tumenggungan Market are as follows :

- Eastern Façade, serves as the main entrance and exit for the market, directly connected to Jl. Kusuma.
- Southern Façade, functions as the entrance to the loading dock, adjacent to Jl. Soekarno-Hatta, the primary city corridor, contributing to congestion in the main urban corridor.
- Northern Façade, serves as the exit for the loading dock and borders Jl. Kolopaking, a small to medium scale commercial area.

Site Characteristics

Figure 12. Area Typology Comparison

Based on the comparison of area typologies presented above, Tumenggungan Market can be classified as a central urban market (Urban Core Market) with the following characteristics ;

- Located in the center of Kebumen City, within a designated heritage area.
- Proximity to commercial, educational, and government functions.
- Multi-functional with a high intensity of activities, deeply rooted in the urban life of Kebumen.
- Serves as a social and communal space for the local community.

Building / Object Characteristics

Figure 13. Object Characteristics Comparison

Based on the comparison diagram of object characteristics presented above, Tumenggungan Market can be described as having the following characteristics :

- Traditional Retail Market, functioning primarily as a local marketplace for goods and commodities.
- Socio-Cultural Community Space, serving as a social and cultural hub for the local community.
- Urban Commercial Node, forming an integral part of the city's commercial and trading system.

Formulation of the Revitalization Direction for Tumenggungan Market

Revitalization Aspect	Existing Issues	Revitalization Direction
Architectural Identity	Building façades are generic and do not reflect local identity.	Strengthening heritage identity through reinterpretation of local elements.
Spatial Layout, Zoning, and Circulation	Commodity zones are disorganized and mixed. Circulation paths are narrow and inadequate.	Clear and functional zoning arrangement, with improved circulation quality and comfort.
Market Social Function	The market space is not fully optimized for social interaction.	Reinforcing the market as a social and communal space.
Tropical Climate Response	Buildings are thermally uncomfortable with minimal natural ventilation.	Optimizing passive strategies based on local climate conditions.
Building Materials	Predominant materials are not contextually appropriate.	Use of materials consistent with local context and climate.
Visual Quality and Heritage Integration	Store façades are inconsistent, and the visual character of the area is unorganized.	Integrating and harmonizing the market's visual appearance with the surrounding heritage area.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study emphasizes that the revitalization of Tumenggungan Market should be directed toward strengthening the city's heritage identity. Local values and social character serve as the foundation, supported by a comprehensive site analysis, including visual and climatic aspects, to maximize the reflection of Kebumen's distinctive character. Consequently, the proposed revitalization focuses on the reinterpretation of local architectural elements, functional zoning and circulation improvements, and enhancing comfort through the use of climate-responsive materials. These strategies are expected to enhance the market's functionality as a traditional urban market while simultaneously reinforcing its heritage identity within the cultural context of Kebumen.

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